

Financial and Monetary Variables Role in Economic Growth of Iraq

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Abstract: Background: The impact of economic policies on economic activities is one of the important topics in macroeconomic analysis, which is still debated. While proponents of the monetary school see monetary policy as the most effective, we find that Keynesian proponents emphasize the importance of fiscal policy in achieving economic growth. So the aim of the current research was to Studying the impact of monetary policies on growth by estimating and analyzing the impact of monetary variables towards financial variables on economic growth.

Methods: Data was collected from Central Bank of Iraq, the present study included, which the variable (GDP growth) is the dependent variable, in the current study, there will be a set of simple standard models for describing money supply. As an independent variable consisting of a group of sub-independent variables, through these following variables (Exports of goods and service, Final consumption expenditure, Trade of GDP. When using regression analysis, it is customary to analyze the predictive ability of a multi-economic model that includes two or more independent variables with a dependent variable.

Results: the outcomes of this research based on the estimation of regression models using ARDL has been showed that the monetary and financial variables have a statistically significant and positive effect on economic growth in Iraqi.

Key words: ARDL, monetary, financial; Economic growth.

1-1 Introduction

Studying the impact of monetary policies on growth by estimating and analyzing the impact of monetary variables towards financial variables on economic growth.

1-2 Relationships between monetary and financial variables on economic growth in Iraq

The impact of economic policies on economic activities is one of the important topics in macroeconomic analysis, which is still debated. While proponents of the monetary school see monetary policy as the most effective, we find that Keynesian proponents emphasize the importance of fiscal policy in achieving economic growth. The actions of the government to influence the GDP and achieve several economic goals, the most important of which is increasing the growth rate, achieving full employment and price stability, are known as economic policies, which are divided into two important parts. concerning its expenditures and revenues, while monetary policy uses the legal reserve ratio, the discount rates, and open markets operation as tools to achieve economic goals.

However, the effectiveness of the performance of each of the two policies depends on the structural structure of the economy. Supporters of the monetary school have emphasized that inflation causes economic development, an increase in the growth-rates of the money supplies causes a decrease in consumption function and an increase in the capital intensity function, in which the average labor productivity has a positive relationship with capital intensity. And so the question can be raised: Can an increase in the inflation rate in the money supply cause growth in Iraq? We will try to answer this question through our research.

The research problem in the existing debate was identified to determine the role of money in influencing real variables in the short run and its neutrality in the long run.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of monetary policies on growth by estimating and analyzing the impact of monetary variables compared to financial variables on economic growth.

While the research hypothesis was defined as follows: in an economy with moderate inflation or fixed prices, does the increase in money supply have a positive effect on GDP in countries with low and moderate inflation, and what is the size of the effect?

HO: An increase in the money supply does not lead to GDP growth

H1: An increase in money supply leads to the growth of GD

1-3 Problem Statement

To clarify the cause of increase in money supply in order to have a positive impact on the gross domestic product in Iraq and inflation and what is the size of the impact?

Increasing of money supply does not result in growth in GDP: Ho

Increasing of the money supply can lead to a growth in GDP: 1 H)

1-4 Research Questions

1. Does an increase in money supply has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Iraq?
2. Does an increase in market value of stock market has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Iraq?

1-5 Research Hypothesis

1. An increase in money supply has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Iraq.
2. An increase in market value of stock market has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Iraq.

1-6 Research Objectives

Studying the impact of monetary policies on growth by estimating and analyzing the impact of monetary variables towards financial variables on economic growth.

1-7 Information collection method

In this dissertation, statistical information was collected from the, Iraqi central Bank, then data were studied by statistical methods.

1-8 Scope of research

Spatial areas: Iraqi country

Temporal areas: 1970-2021

Thematic area: Economic growth in Iraq

2- Literature Review

2-1 Theoretical Foundations

2-1-1 Stock Market and Iraqi growth rate

Unlike other market, a country stock markets deal with acquiring securities and selling like share. The stock markets is critical in nation economy of Iraq to be form on solid grounds. It is economic relevances result from two factor (1). Firstly, it give the mean to increases economic investments. Secondly, it foster healthy rivalry in businesse and stimulate business effective-ness on the parts of individual businesse, here promoting economic growths. Third, it provide aplatform for

individual and organization to utilize their fund to sustain and profit the living standard. As potential customer, these individual contributes to their respective nation economic progresses (2).

2-1-2 Macroeconomic Variable in Iraq

Various macro economic factor like GDP growth, inflation, employment rates, national income and lending interest rates impacts the stock returns. There was inflations when there was an increasing in the price of service and good in economy. Typically, economic activities were brisk in those circumstance, and there was a struggle to improving production to increase sales. Moreover, the improved financial condition enable the corporation to provide big stock return (3). The rises GDP growth indicate economic advancements and improved technological and economic resource. So, increase business profitability and efficiency incentivize corporation to boost stocks return (4, 5).

2-1-3 Money supply and public finance in Iraq

Declining oil revenue and subdued economic activities continue to exerted pressure on governments financial in 2020. Iraq fiscal situations was highly dependent on oil receipt as it constitute ninety two percent of the total revenue in 2019 (as 35.9 percentage of gross domestic production, Figures 2-1). As such it fiscal situations was highly affect by volatility in the global oil market. Cut in oil productions due to production cap and lower price have result in 48.3 percentage (year/year) drops in revenue in first eight month of 2020 (8M20) (6). Furthermore, the Parliament and GoI had been less activity on reform to domestic revenues mobilization. Despite custom and taxes effort, non oil revenue shared in total budgets had remained lower in 2019 at 7.0 percentage of gross domestic production. Furthermore, subdued economic activities led to a decline of 38.3 percentage (year/year) in 8M20 non oil revenue due to COVID19 following lockdown and health mitigations measure. As a result of those event, the budgets surplus in 2019 changes to a deficit of 5.5 percentage of gross domestic production in 8M20 (7).

since 2006 Iraq regional government had presented a remarkable economic growth especially if we take GDP as an indicator. That economic growth continued till 2014 but suddenly the flow of money from Baghdad stopped, foreign direct investment in both countries has been developed. Iraq has a very poor banking system. In addition, both countries have difficulties with labor force. Today's market demands are very high in regard to the professionalism. Furthermore, there is an imbalance in the sectors which have been licensed by Iraq for investment. For example, housing sector has received the biggest portion of the money and more than 13% is provided to that sector. As Iraq trying to stand on its own feet, it has to build a strong infrastructure through foreign direct investment (8, 9).

3- Research Methodology

3-1 Introduction of indicators, variables, their measurement methods, studies of the data and information, and the method of analysis

Interest in economic growth appeared in the writings of Adam Smith, Robert Malthus, Ricardo, John Stuart Mill, and others, who believed that economic growth would stop in the long run and that investment was the only solution. In the short term, traditionalists have assumed that economic growth occurs as a result of high profits and the occurrence of capital accumulation, and accordingly, the second chapter deals with theories of economic growth, beginning with Harrod Dumar's theories of growth without money. And Solo, in preparation for Theories of Growth with Money, deals with the effect of money on growth in detail.

3-2 Research model and variables

The determinants of fiscal and monetary impacts will analyzed using the co-integration method. Different tests allow testing the existence or lack of an integration relationship between the variables of an econometric model. However, the Co-Integration by Delay or Auto Regressive distributed Lags (ARDL) approach of co-integration proposed by Pesaran et al., (1999, 2001) is

increasingly used in research. This choice is justified by the fact that this technique has the advantage of being more efficient for small sample studies and is applicable to the series to be integrated in order 1, level 0 or mutually integrated; in contrast to traditional integration tests such as those of Engle Granger (1987), the Johansen test (1988) and the Johansen and Juselius' test (1990). However, the technique ceases to be applicable when the series order of integration is greater than 1. Another advantage of this method is that it allows to estimate the long- and short-term dynamics in the same econometric model (10-12). Our data for the ARDL specification of the relationship between the, public expenditure and money supply is represented by equation 1: which represent the standard model equation includes two types of variables: external variables (independent) which include liquidity and government spending. Internal variables include GDP growth as a dependent variable and money supply in Iraq. The equation of the model can be formulated as follows:

$$t - 1 + \beta X t - 1 + t - 1) + 2t) + t + \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

it is:

Δ =Represents the first difference

The first equation is presented according to the following formula:

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where :

Y is the dependent variable indicating rate of economic growth

X1 is money supply

X2 market value of Iraq'a stock market

X3 is government size

(GDP) measures the monetary value of final goods and services

1. Public expenditure
2. (M2)Extensive Money supply

3-3 Model Methodology

Base on the model introduced in chapter three we are going to estimate these equations, this model by the method of ARDL and then we estimate the model by listed the results in tables and discussing each table, the most important part of discussion was testing the hypothesis we want to test the important variables of Iraqi government size have or have not positive significant and positive impacts on economic growth and the coefficient is how much, then discussing about the results of the model and their expressing as effective factors in Iraqi economy (13).

3-3-1 Description and construction of the Standard Model

The econometric model is defined as a statistical model used in econometrics. Where the econometric model focuses on describing the statistical relationship that is believed to bear between various economic quantities and is related to the studied economic phenomenon. An econometric model It is possible for an economic phenomenon to be a random model. In addition, it is also possible to study econometric models that are not linked to any specific economic theory. In order to obtain a good standard model, it is necessary to know the components of this model, which best represents the studied economic phenomenon, because the description of a good standard model will be reflected in the description of the logical relationships between the variables of the studied model. Therefore, in the economic measurement model, describing its variables is a very important step. Thus, the symbols of the variables included in the current study can be clarified as follows (14).

Table No. (3-1) shows the names and abbreviations of the dependent and independent variables of the standard models studied.

Name	Symbol
GDP Growth Annual	GDP.G.A
Trade of GDP	T.GDP
Exports of Goods and Service	E.G.S
Final Consumption Expenditure	F.C.E
Money Supply	M.S

3-3-1-1 t-test

It is one of the important statistical tests in clarifying the significance of the estimated parameters of the important economic variables that are included in building the standard model. As this test is very important in demonstrating the reliability (significance) of the estimated parameters of this model. In this test, there are two main hypotheses, the first is the null hypothesis (H_0): which states that ((there is no significant effect of the economic variable x in the studied model)) and against this hypothesis is the alternative hypothesis (H_1): ((there is a significant effect of the economic variable x in the model The studied)) and the mathematical formulation of the two hypotheses above can be as follows (15)

$$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0, \text{ Alternative hypothesis vs } H_0: \beta_i = 0 \text{ where } i = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

The independent variables number is p

In the t-test, the computed t-value is compared with the tabular t-value (statistical tables for the t-student distribution). If the calculated value of t is greater than the tabular value of t, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject (1) the null hypothesis, meaning that the economic variable has a significant effect in the studied model, and vice versa.

3-3-1-2 F test

The F distribution test is considered one of the important tests in standard models. This test shows the possibility of the studied standard model in representing the studied economic phenomenon. That is, it shows the quality of reconciliation between the studied variables for a particular economic phenomenon. Also, in the F test, there are two hypotheses that are tested: the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis. And that the statistical decision-making regarding the rejection or acceptance of the null hypothesis or the alternative hypothesis depends on the following rule, if the calculated F is greater than the tabular F (a tabular value extracted from the F-distribution tables). We will accept the alternative hypothesis and in turn reject the null hypothesis.

3-3-1-3 Lab Test Selection

It is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be predicted from the independent variable(s), which reveals the explanatory power between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The correlation coefficient is denoted by the following symbol, R^2 . The coefficient of determination is defined as the square of the correlation coefficient. The coefficient of determination is defined in the following closed period [0,100], but in standard tests, the corrected coefficient of determination is relied upon, which is calculated from dividing the coefficient of determination by the correction fraction. Thus, whenever the correction factor approaches 100, it indicates the high explanatory potential of the independent variables on the dependent variable. If the rate correction coefficient approaches zero, it indicates a weakness in the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable,

3-3-1-4 Time series analysis

The Time Series Analysis method is one of the statistical methods worthy of attention, especially in economic phenomena that are exposed to hidden seasonal changes on the one hand, and on the other hand, most of the data of economic phenomena are collected during certain periods of time,

i.e. depend on a certain time range (several years, for example) , then it predicts the future based on the different values that appeared in the time series and the growth pattern in the values; In this way, it is superior to the traditional method, as the traditional method calculates the value difference between only two times of the time series and builds future predictions on their basis, without taking into account the general pattern of the series or the rise and fall of the connected time series values. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the time series of data related to economic phenomena in order to find out the stability of the variables of the economic study and to know the statistical characteristics of these variables under the phenomenon (1 and 2) (16, 17).

3-3-1-5 Testing the autocorrelation problem

The standard model is exposed to a variety of standard problems, and among these problems is the problem of autocorrelation.

If the data required to be studied by regression method are in the form of a time series, the Durban-Watson test can be employed: which focuses on testing two hypotheses (3 and 2): The first is the null hypothesis H_0 , which states ((there is no autocorrelation problem in the standard model)) and the second is the alternative hypothesis H_1 , which states ((there is an autocorrelation problem in the standard model)) and the mathematical formulation of the two hypotheses above can be as follows (18):

$$H_0: \rho = 0$$

$$H_1: \rho \neq 0$$

The Durban-Watson test is calculated using the following mathematical formula

$$D.W = 2(1 - \hat{\rho})$$

Whereas $-1 \leq \hat{\rho} \leq 1$ according to what is shown, the value of (d.w) can be between zero and four the null hypothesis can be rejected or accepted according to the cases shown in the table below.

Table No. (3-2) shows cases of rejecting or accepting the null hypothesis in the Durban-Watson test

Statistical decision	Case	ت
refuse H_0 There is a negative autocorrelation	$4 - d_L < D.W < 4$	1
Nothing can be said for certain (failed test)	$4 - d_U < D.W < 4 - d_L$	2
acceptance H_0 No autocorrelation found	$d_U < D.W < 4 - d_U$	3
Nothing can be said for certain (failed test)	$d_L < D.W < d_U$	4
refuse H_0 There is a positive autocorrelation	$0.0 < D.W < d_L$	5

Where d_U and d_L are tabular values extracted from tables (D.W)

3-3-1-6 Testing the multilinearity problem

The problem of multilinearity can be tested through a set of tests, the most important of which is the test

Farrar& Glauber test

This test was developed in (1967) and is based mainly on the Chi square test to test the following hypothesis:

H_0 : There is no problem of multilinearity

H_1 : There is a problem with multilinearity

Depending on the determinant of the correlation coefficient matrix |R| The number of independent variables (p), the number of experimental units (n), and degrees of freedom $(n(n-1))/2$, and the mathematical formula for it is as follows:

$$\chi_0^2 = - \left[\left[n - 1 - \frac{1}{6}(2p + 5) \right] \ln | R | \right] \dots (4)$$

R: correlation coefficient matrix

p: number of variables,

n: sample size

The result of equation (4) is compared with the tabular value of χ^2 at $(n(n-1))/2$ degrees of freedom, and the alternative hypothesis is rejected if the calculated value is the largest.

3-3-1-7 Dickey-Fuller test (D.F) Dickey fuller

This test focuses on three main components

Formulation of the standard model sample size and level of significance. To complete this test, there are three formulas:

This formula is represented by the absence of a fixed limit and a general trend. This formula can be written (1 and 2).

$$\Delta Y_t = \delta Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

This formula is called a simple random walk.

The second formula contains the fixed term and can be written according to the following formula

$$\Delta Y_t = \mu + \delta Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

This formula is called random walk with drift.

The third formula contains the constant limit and the general temporal trend.

$$\Delta Y_t = \mu + \alpha T + \delta Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

whereas

Δ first order difference δ hysteresis parameter ϵ_t random error term Y_t is the variable to be tested for stability T time trend α time trend parameter

In this test, the focus will be on testing two main hypotheses, the first is the null hypothesis, $H_0: \delta=0$ against a second hypothesis called the alternative hypothesis, $H_1: \delta>0$, where the t-value calculated according to the (D.F) test is compared with the tabular t-value calculated according to the Dickey-Fowler test, which is called the critical value. At a sample size (n) and one of the levels of significance (0.01, 0.05, 0.1), if the calculated value is less than the tabular value, then our statistical decision accepts the null hypothesis and rejects the alternative hypothesis and vice versa.

3-3-1-8 Augment Dickey Fuller (ADF) Augmented Test

In this test we will address the error in the original DF test which neglected the autocorrelation of the error element ϵ_t . Whereas, in the ADF test, a time-slowng variable will be used among the independent variables, as the ADF will be more efficient than the previous test.

$$\Delta Y_t = \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \theta_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

After estimating the parameters of the above equation, the test statistic (Extended Dickey-Fowler Tau) is extracted.

$$\tau = \frac{\hat{\delta}}{S_{\hat{\delta}}}$$

where $S_{\hat{\delta}}$ is the standard deviation of the estimated parameter

If the calculated value is greater than the tabular value of the expanded tau Dickey-Fowler under a certain level of significance and a degree of freedom equal to the sample size, then the null hypothesis that there is a unit root is rejected, meaning that the chain is stable (1).

4- Results

4-1 The dependent variable (GDP growth)

In the current study, there will be a set of standard models in which the variable (GDP growth) is the dependent variable

4-2 Independent variables (explanatory variables or explanatory variables)

In the current study, there will be a set of simple standard models for describing money supply. As an independent variable consisting of a group of sub-independent variables, through these following variables (Exports of goods and service, Final consumption expenditure, Trade of GDP,

4-3: Stability tests of the studied standard models

1- Testing the stability of the time series: The condition of the stability of the time series is considered one of the very important things in the regression analysis of the data that takes the nature of the time series, and knowing that the used time series is stable must achieve a set of statistical characteristics. Where the time series is considered stable (static) if it fulfills the following conditions.

Stability of average values over time $E(y_t) = \mu$

Variation stability over time $Var(y_t) = \sigma^2$

- The variance between any two values of the same variable is dependent on the displacement (slowing down) between the two values and not on the actual value of the time at which the variance is calculated, i.e. (1 and 2)

$$(y_t) = E(y_t - \mu)(y_{t-k} - \mu)$$

Where (k) is the lag time

As we mentioned above, the absence of stability in the time series whose variables the estimators want to calculate by the regression model is false (Spurious), so its estimations in this case will be inaccurate and far from reality and the study does not represent the best representation. It can give us results inflated to the R^2 , t-test, and F-test. There is a collage of new tests that are used to determine stability. We can rely on the graph of the time series variables and judge the stability of the time series. Also, the unit root test can be used, which is considered one of the new tests, in testing the stability of the time series. Also, there are new tests in the time series stability test, which are the simple and expanded Dickey-Fowler test.

4-4 Building the economic model

When using regression analysis, it is customary to analyze the predictive ability of a multi-economic model that includes two or more independent variables with a dependent variable.

One of the first works that must be done in the subject of regression is to characterize the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable in order to determine the variables that will be included in the model, and this can only be done with the help of economic theory. The strength of the correlation does not necessarily mean the existence of a causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, but it remains among the important indicators in describing the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. In the current study, various scenarios will be built for economic measurement models according to the hypotheses of the current study. And as follows

4-4-1 Impact of (M.S) on GDP.G.A

According to the current standard model, we find that (GDP. Annual Growth) represents the dependent variable that is affected by the independent variable (money supply). After determining the main parts of this standard model, it can be formulated mathematically according to the following model.

$$GDP.G.A = \beta_0 + \beta_1(M.S)_i + \epsilon_i, i = 1,2 \dots 52$$

whereas

β_0 is a constant and (β_1) represents the estimated parameter of the above model

ϵ_i is the random error term that is distributed according to a normal distribution with a mean equal to zero and a variance equal to σ^2

4-4-2 The effect of (T.GDP) on GDP.G.A

According to the current standard model, we find that (GDP. Annual Growth) represents the dependent variable that is affected by the independent variable (Trade of GDP). After determining the main parts of this standard model, it can be formulated mathematically according to the following model.

$$GDP.G.A = \beta_0 + \beta_1(T.GDP)_i + \epsilon_i, i = 1,2 \dots 52$$

whereas

β_0 is a constant and (β_1) represents the estimated parameter of the above model

ϵ_i is the random error term that is distributed according to a normal distribution with a mean equal to zero and a variance equal to σ^2 .

4-4-3 Impact of (E.G.S) on GDP.G.A

According to the current standard model, we find that (GDP. Annual Growth) represents the dependent variable that is affected by the independent variable (Exports of goods and service). After determining the main parts of this standard model, it can be formulated mathematically according to the following model.

$$GDP.G.A = \beta_0 + \beta_1(E.G.S)_i + \epsilon_i, i = 1,2 \dots 52$$

whereas

β_0 is a constant and (β_1) represents the estimated parameter of the above model

ϵ_i is the random error term that is distributed according to a normal distribution with a mean equal to zero and a variance equal to σ^2 .

4-4-4 Impact of (FCE) on GDP.G.A

According to the current standard model, we find that (GDP. Annual Growth) represents the dependent variable that is affected by the independent variable (Final consumption Expenditure). After determining the main parts of this standard model, it can be formulated mathematically according to the following model.

$$GDP.G.A = \beta_0 + \beta_1(FCE)_i + \epsilon_i, i = 1,2 \dots 52$$

whereas

β_0 is a constant and (β_1) represents the estimated parameter of the above model

ϵ_i is the random error term that is distributed according to a normal distribution with a mean equal to zero and a variance equal to σ^2 .

4-5 The second topic General standard methods

4-5-1 Test the hypotheses of the linear model

To obtain good estimates with high predictive ability, a set of criteria must be applied

1- The economic criterion: the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable is described according to the estimators' indication in the studied model, and the results of the analysis of the studied relationship must be in accordance with the logic of the economic theory.

2- Statistical standard: In this standard, the possibility of relying on the capabilities of the studied standard model is clarified, such as the ability to predict or the possibility of generalizing this model and so on. One of the special statistical methods in building the standard model is

3- Testing the stability of the remainder if there are two series of values for the variables (y_t) and (x_t). The remainders of these two series have a cointegration defined by the following mathematical expression

$(u_t, \epsilon_t) \sim I(0)$ That is, the time series is stable. If there is no co-integration between the two variables, this means that the series of residuals will be unstable. One of the most important tests used to measure the stability of the time series through the residuals is the test .

3-1 Phelps-Perron test: This test is named after Peter C.B. Phillips and Peer-Perron. Where this test focuses on eliminating the effects of autocorrelation from the remainder of the unit root test equation, as it depends on the differences. This test has been described as the best test in the time series stability test for variables, as it focuses on the equation presented in the modified Dickey-Fowler test, which is known as.

$$\Delta y_t = (1 - \rho)y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

It differs from the modified Dickey-Fowler test that does not depend on time differences, as well as differs in the treatment of heterogeneity and the treatment of autocorrelation, where the Phelps-Peyron test relies on non-significant corrections in obtaining the t-test statistics, in contrast to the modified Dickey-Fowler test that faces inconsistency Homogeneity and autocorrelation for adding differences.

4- The method of least squares and its assumptions

Most of the social and economic researches focus on studying the relationship between more than two variables. The standard model generally focuses on the existence of a linear relationship between a dependent variable (Y_i) and a number of independent variables ($X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p$) and the random error limit ϵ_i where n is the number of observations and p is the number of independent variables. From the above data, the multiple regression model described thus can be obtained (3).

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip} + \epsilon_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

The above model can be summarized

$$Y_i = \sum_{j=0}^p \beta_j X_{ij} + \epsilon_i$$

Where $X_{i0} = 0$

The above model contains $(p + 1)$ of the parameters to be estimated, and the first parameter of these parameters is called the fixed term and is symbolized by the symbol β_0 , and in order to obtain estimators smoothly, the concept of matrices and vectors must be used, as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \vdots \\ Y_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & X_{11} & X_{12} & \dots & X_{1p} \\ 1 & X_{21} & X_{22} & \dots & X_{2p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & X_{n1} & X_{n2} & \dots & X_{np} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_p \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \vdots \\ \epsilon_n \end{bmatrix}$$

The above standard form written in matrix form can be rewritten in an abbreviated form as in the following form

$$Y = X\beta + \epsilon$$

whereas

Y is a vector with order (n×1) of the observations of the dependent variable

X is called the information matrix and has a capacity of n×(p+1) for the observations of the independent variables

β is the vector of the features to be estimated, and this vector is of order x1 (k+1).

ε is the n×1 random error vector

4-1 Method of least squares estimation in the multiple regression model

To focus on estimating the features vector β that goes back to the multiple regression model for p from the independent variables and a vector that represents the random error limit that is distributed according to the normal distribution with an average of zero, that is.

$$E(\epsilon) = \begin{bmatrix} E(\epsilon_1) \\ E(\epsilon_2) \\ \vdots \\ E(\epsilon_n) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

A contrast and a common variation is defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} Var(\epsilon) &= E(\epsilon\epsilon) = E\left(\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \vdots \\ \epsilon_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 & \epsilon_2 & \dots & \epsilon_n \end{bmatrix}\right) \\ Var(\epsilon) &= \begin{bmatrix} E(\epsilon_1^2) & E(\epsilon_1\epsilon_2) & \dots & E(\epsilon_1\epsilon_n) \\ E(\epsilon_2\epsilon_1) & E(\epsilon_2^2) & \dots & E(\epsilon_2\epsilon_n) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ E(\epsilon_n\epsilon_1) & E(\epsilon_n\epsilon_2) & \dots & E(\epsilon_n^2) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

whereas

$$, E(\epsilon_i\epsilon_j) = 0 \quad i \neq j, E(\epsilon_i^2) = \sigma_\epsilon^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} Var(\epsilon) &= \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_\epsilon^2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_\epsilon^2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \sigma_\epsilon^2 \end{bmatrix} \\ Var(\epsilon) &= \sigma_\epsilon^2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \sigma_\epsilon^2 I_n \end{aligned}$$

Where I_n is the unit matrix with amplitude (n×n).

To get good estimates, the model must be free of standard problems. For example, it is required that there is no complete or almost complete linear relationship (perfect polylinearity) between the independent variables g .

Conclusion

We conclude that there is an agreement between economic schools that there are two basic mechanisms through which monetary policy affects economic activities, through changes in income to Price. Level.

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